

Entrepreneurs are the center of value creation

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The proposal to build a monument to entrepreneurs helps people always remember those who have created jobs for them, created products and services to serve their lives and are the source of a prosperous and happy life. At the same time, it also inspires the spirit and aspiration to contribute to work and pursue the values of each person in society.

In the economy, there are mainly two subjects participating in transactions in the market, including producers and consumers. Entrepreneurs represent the production side, to survive and develop, they need to understand the "pain" and aspirations of consumers. On that basis, entrepreneurs lead businesses to develop product and service ideas that create high benefits for users. At that time, users are willing to pay high prices, so businesses can also sell at high prices and have good profits.

Business is a competitive process to bring benefits to many customers. In a broader sense, the business process is a competitive process in the process of building civilization and human progress. The entrepreneur is

the captain leading the workers to steer the ship in the process of building civilization.

This process includes a series of activities that are of a civilization-building nature. To create useful products and services, entrepreneurs must invest in research on production technology with innovations in processes, methods, equipment and factories serving production. Society thus accumulates higher-level technology, and cities become more beautiful thanks to more spacious constructions. If entrepreneurs do not have a creative spirit, there will be no new constructions or new technologies.

To operate new technology to create new products, it is necessary to have a team of human resources with appropriate qualifications. The enterprise itself is the place to effectively train workers with new skills suitable for operating the enterprise according to its own strategy. Thanks to that, the level and skills of workers are improved. Not only that, the enterprise itself is an important place to nurture good values and qualities for workers thanks to humane and highly disciplined regulations and processes.

It is not difficult to see that universities impart knowledge and skills to learners from knowledge invented and created by the business community. Most of the production and management technologies are invented at businesses. Universities, through research and testing programs at businesses, develop theories and lectures to convey to learners. Through this, it can be seen that entrepreneurs play an important role in developing technology and human resources for society.

To operate a business effectively, not only knowledge, skills, technology, capital are needed, but also the important thing is to establish a working and behavioral routine between people in the business. Entrepreneurs are the center of creating, nurturing and spreading good values and behavioral standards for the business community. Thanks to that, corporate culture with civilized values is formed and spread throughout society.

To motivate workers to be creative, entrepreneurs implement many measures to motivate them spiritually and materially. Not only helping workers take care of their own lives and their families, businesses also pay insurance and have policies to take care of workers' lives, helping many people to be warm and happy. It can be said that entrepreneurs are the ones who are happy after everyone else, and worry before all workers.

Direct and indirect taxes from businesses are the main source of revenue for the State budget. This revenue is used by the State to manage society, develop infrastructure, and subsidize the disadvantaged in society. On the other hand, when the country faces many problems such as epidemic disasters, floods, and even wars, businessmen are always the leading force in contributing materially, as well as human resources and methods to solve problems.

Entrepreneurs create businesses that are not just their own, but have a distinct mission, a place to gather people with the same ideals, pursue the same value system and serve specific customers. In fact, there are many businesses that have lasted over time through many different generations of entrepreneurs. Each entrepreneur has a certain age, but the values they create can last forever.

The core of every economy operates to create value for human life, that process will create many jobs for society and contribute to the State budget. Thanks to that, we can create the prospect of a rich people, a strong country of a prosperous nation. The key to that core is the creative role of entrepreneurs.

Therefore, society needs to be grateful to entrepreneurs, those who create wealth and jobs for society. The State needs to honor the mission and role of entrepreneurs as a way to encourage and motivate everyone in society to strive to pursue values. And the proposal to build a monument to entrepreneurs will help people always remember those who have created jobs for them, created products and services to serve life and the source of a prosperous and happy life. At the same time, it also inspires the spirit and aspiration to contribute to work and pursue values of each person in society.